

USING DEVELOPMENTAL ACTIVITIES FOR IMPROVING EFL LEARNERS' SPEAKING SKILLS

Abduqodirova Yulduz Safaraliyevna
Phd student of NSPI

Annotation: The article is dedicated to the actual problems relevant to speaking in the process of learning a foreign language. The authors have proposed the solutions to the obstacles on analyzing them thoroughly.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqola chet tilini o'rganish jarayonida, so'zlash mahoratiga oid haqiqatda yuzaga keladigan muammolarga bag'ishlanadi. Mualliflar muammolarni batafsil o'rgangan holda ularga mutanosib yechimlarni taklif etib o'tdilar.

Key words: Speaking skills, communicative activities, text, drill, L1, L2, antonyms, synonyms, phrasal words, idioms, erroneous speech, ratio.

Kalit so'zlar: So'zlash mahorati, aloqa qilishga doir mashqlar, matn, mashq (mashg'ulot), birinchi til (ona tili), ikkinchi til (ona tilidan keyingi darajadagi til), antonimlar, sinonimlar, fraziologik so'zlar, idiomalar, xatolarga boy nutq, nisbat.

It is widely known that the English language is spreading over the world where each person is having the wish of connecting. Yet, a great number of learners meet with various obstacles in the process of learning this language. Issues such as having a rich vocabulary, speaking fluently without any grammatical error and being a persistent learner are still considered to be the most difficult problems for language learners.

It is obvious that speaking is “the process of building and sharing meaning through the use of verbal and non-verbal symbols, in a variety of contexts”⁶⁶.

From the points of view of Chaney it can be concluded that speaking is a crucial part of the second language learning and teaching. Despite its importance, teaching speaking has been undervalued and English language teachers have continued to teach speaking just as making a repetition of drills and memorization

⁶⁶ Chaney, A.L., T.L. Burk. Teaching oral communication in Grades K-8. Allyn & Heinle. -Boston, -1998.

of texts for numerous years. According to the requirement of the modern world the target of teaching speaking is to improve students' communicative skills, because only by this way learners can express themselves well in a foreign language and learn how to follow the social and cultural rules appropriate to any communicative circumstance.

The spoken language is both interactional and transactional, but what should teachers focus on in class? On having investigated this issue thoroughly, well-known scientists Brown and Yule suggested their own methods. In accordance with their conception while teaching the spoken language, teachers of foreign languages should:

- focus on teaching longer transactional turns. Even native speakers have difficulty with them and learners of ESL need to be able to communicate efficiently whether in their own country or abroad;
- teach interactional language by using an awareness-raising approach. For instance, with monolingual classes by listening to a recorded L1 conversation before a similar L2 recording.

In spite of possessing a strong desire and trying, a good number of learners undergo hardships speaking English confidently because of the shortage of necessary vocabulary. Apparently, it is inappropriate to start speaking English without a quantum of sufficient words. Learners are able to improve their speaking skills with the help of using a good number of exercises. In the first step, learning a great number of texts on different themes such as “Healthy eating”, “Green-packaging”, “Parental aspiration” “What makes a person educated”⁶⁷ by heart and being used to retell them couple of times is a productive way to develop speaking. This is the fact that while learning texts pupils come across new words and they are demanded to work on the vocabulary. In such kind of situations learners must use all new words in their daily speech to make them more stable in their memory. Moreover, learning antonyms-synonyms, phrasal verbs and idioms and making up

⁶⁷ Betty Kirkpatrick, Rebecca Mok, “Read and understand 1” Learners Publishing Pte Ltd 222 Tagore Lane, #03-01 TG Building, Singapore 787603, -2005

sentences by adding each of them is also a good way to raise an oral communication.

After for about three months or so, it can be realized the result of trainings. The most wonderful thing is that if learners have to speak on a theme by chance, it occurs by the absence of difficulties.

On the other hand, we may follow an evident that most speakers make considerable mistakes during their speech unconsciously even they have a tough base. It is true that a speaker cannot attract listeners by their erroneous speech in spite of great vocabulary. In this position, listeners begin to pay attention to their mistakes and more or less all the time they count their mistakes inspire of them. The best solution is to train to speak having both fluent and grammatical clear language. In other words, before having a speech at lessons or in other places one should try to do it on their own by imagining a real atmosphere and of course while speaking avoid to make grammatical mistakes.

It should be pointed out that learning a foreign language depends on one's character too. To learn the language, one should have some qualities of positive manners. Firstly, each learner should be attentive during classes. Because, the attention helps to acquire profound knowledge and comprehend the material better. Secondly, it is significant to be an industrious, strong-willed and persistent person for achieving success.

It is worth to point out despite the fact that a number of students have been learning the English language for a long time they cannot express themselves well and confidently. The main reason for it is wasting a great deal of time studying theory approximately: 70-80 % and it is almost lack of time to deal with practice: 30-20% Any foreign language must be learnt in order to communicate using appropriate grammatical rules for speaking in a perfect way.

According to our thorough survey, we have come to the conclusion: The ratio of theory to practice must be 30 % of theory to 70 % of practice. For achieving the fixed result, the following important and essential actions must be carried out:

- 1) Grammatical rules must be used in speech instantly after learning them
- 2) Learners should speak and listen to the speech as much as possible
- 3) Students have to think in a target language (English), not in a native language

REFERENCES:

1. A.A.Abduazizov. English phonetics. Publishing house "Musiqqa". Tashkent, 2007
2. Betty Kirkpatrick, Rebecca Mok, "Read and understand 1" Learners Publishing Pte Ltd 222 Tagore Lane, #03-01 TG Building, Singapore 787603, 2005
3. Chaney A. L. , T.L .Burk. Teaching oral communication in Grades K-8. Allyn&Heinle. Boston,1998.
4. J.J.Jalolov, G.T.Makhkamova, Sh.S.Ashurov. English language teaching methodology.Fan va texnologiya. Tashkent, 2015
5. [http: //iteslj.org/Articles/Kayi-Teaching Speaking. Htm J](http://iteslj.org/Articles/Kayi-Teaching Speaking. Htm J)

LEARNING THEORIES IN TEACHING ENGLISH AND THEIR IMPORTANCE

Akramova Aziza Sediya kizi

1st year Master's Degree student

National University of Uzbekistan, Tashkent

Sotlikova Rima Olimjonovna

Phd, associate professor

National University of Uzbekistan, Tashkent

Annotation: The thesis discusses different theories of language acquisition which are important in teaching and learning English. As language acquisition refers to how humans can develop the ability to understand and use language,